

**ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AMONG THE HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL
STUDENTS OF RAIPUR DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT:

Academic procrastination is a prevalent phenomenon in educational contexts, particularly among higher secondary school students. It refers to the voluntary delay of academic tasks despite the knowledge of negative consequences. The study aims to understand the various factors influencing procrastination in higher education settings, with particular attention to gender differences and the influence of geographical location. In this study the researcher select randomly 200 higher secondary school students. Findings suggest that there was no significant difference on procrastination behavior based on gender and residential background, with male students exhibiting higher levels of procrastination compared to their female counterparts, and rural students experiencing more difficulties in managing their academic tasks compared to their urban peers, both urban and rural area students are showing procrastination behavior for their study. Urban area students have variety of distraction for their study. After study the researcher suggest the parents, teachers and also education policy makers to identify procrastination underlying causes like time management, sincerity and task pervasiveness.

Keywords:- Academic procrastination, Higher education students.

INTRODUCTION :

Academic procrastination is defined as the deliberate delay of academic tasks, despite the awareness of potential negative consequences. This phenomenon is pervasive among higher education students and can have a substantial impact on their academic performance, mental health, and overall well-being. Procrastination often leads to poor time management, missed deadlines, and increased stress, which in turn affect students' academic outcomes and personal development.

While procrastination has been studied widely, less attention has been given to how gender and residential location (rural vs. urban) affect procrastination behaviors. Gender differences in procrastination have been documented in some studies, but the evidence remains inconclusive. Similarly, students from rural and urban areas may experience different academic challenges and coping mechanisms, which could influence their tendency to procrastinate.

This study seeks to bridge these gaps by exploring academic procrastination among higher education students in a comprehensive manner, comparing male and female students, as well as those from rural and urban backgrounds.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE:

(Kuftyak, 2021) Studied on “*Procrastination and academic performance in students*” in this study the researcher studied about the link between the academic procrastination, stress depression and anxiety. This study implemented on 435 students between the age group of 17-25 years old. The researcher found that the students had low academic performance were inclined to more often suffer from procrastination. The correlation analysis shows that a high level of procrastination is related to stress and academic failure. The analyze of links between procrastination and stressors, and also reactions on it among students has shown that the higher the social anxiety, failure avoidance, procrastination frequency, lazy, worse perfectionism and impulsive, the higher he values all stressors and impressive of reactions on it.

In this way, academic procrastination impedes the effectiveness of student study, effects on performance, contributes to stress, that undoubtedly impacts on professional development of future specialists.

According to (Varalakshmi, 2021) There are many factors influencing academic procrastination, such as internet addiction, self – efficacy, time management, motivation and stress. One of the impacts of academic procrastination is academic performance. The purpose of this research is to analyze factors influence procrastination among college students in Cikarang – Bekasi. Researcher analyzed data that gathered from 139 students filled the questionnaire, using path analysis – PLS. Sample in this research were college students batch 2016 – 2019. The result of this research show that most of proposed hypotheses in the model were accepted. Some hypotheses stated that Internet Addiction has no significant effect on time management, Internet Addiction has no significant indirect effect on academic procrastination through time management, Motivation has no significant effect on academic procrastination, Stress has no significant effect on time management and stress has no significant effect on academic procrastination through time management.

(Gohain & Gogoi, 2021)Conduct the study on title “*A study on the Reason of Academic procrastination among college students*” Academic procrastination is often seen among college students at each academic level. It includes underestimating the time needed to complete an academic task, excuses for poor performance in a task, missing deadlines to important tasks like submission of assignments, projects, preparation for exams, etc. Most students were not aware of their postponing behavior and unintentionally delay the task. Since the college students are packed with different academic tasks that are needed to be accomplished within the designated time frame, but students fail to complete their tasks on time due to many reasons such as the influence of technology, use of social media, peer pressure, and overload of work, etc. The present study was an attempt to study the academic procrastination among College students of Jorhat, Assam, India in the year 2020. The study was conducted on 199 numbers of undergraduate students. Samples were selected with the help of Solvin’s formula and proportionate allocation. In this study apart from the standard tool i.e. Procrastination Assessment Scale for Students (PASS)”, an interview schedule was used to check the background information of the respondents and other reasons leading towards academic procrastination among students. The researcher found that respondents were high and low procrastinators due to various reasons such as 68.9 percent were high procrastinators as they waited until a classmate did his or hers so that he or she could give some advice (dependency). On the other hand, 72.8 percent were found to be low procrastinators in the task look forward to the excitement of doing the task at the last minute (risk-taking). Therefore understanding and determining the reasons that are leading towards academic procrastination will help the students in decreasing their delaying behavior.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To explore gender differences in academic procrastination.
 - Compare procrastination behaviors between male and female students.
2. To investigate differences in procrastination based on residential background (rural vs. urban).
 - Analyze how students from rural and urban settings differ in their academic procrastination patterns.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

H1: There will be no significant difference on levels of academic procrastination among Male higher education students compare to their counterpart female higher education students.

H2: There will be no significant difference on levels of academic procrastination among urban higher education students compare to rural higher education students.

Method

To conduct a smooth study the researcher follows the systematic method. The researcher used descriptive survey method in this study.

Sample

The researcher selects 200 samples out of them 100 male and 100 female of higher education students of Raipur district. It was further categories by urban and rural students. Samples are selected from the total population through random sampling.

Tool

In the present study the researcher selected and uses the following tool to collect the data “Academic Procrastination Scale” by Dr. Savita Gupta and Liyaqat Bashir.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA:

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant difference on levels of academic procrastination among Male higher education students compare to their counterpart female higher education students.

* Table value 1.96 with df 198 on 0.05 level of significance.

Category	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Significance level
Male	100	83.25	16.86	0.007	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Female	100	77.01	15.64		

Mean of the male student was 83.25 where as

sd was 16.86, female students mean was 77.01 and sd was 15.64. In this calculation the t-value was 0.007 where calculated table value was 1.96 which was greater than the t-value. So the calculation proves that there was no significant difference between levels of academic procrastination among the male and female students of higher education.

Bar Graph -1

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference on levels of academic procrastination among urban higher education students compare to rural higher education students.

* Table value 1.96 with df 98 on 0.05 level of significance.

Mean of the urban male student was 88.34 where as sd was 15.81 and rural male students mean was 78.16

and sd was 16.47

In this

Locale	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Significance level
Urban	Male	50	88.34	15.81	0.0021	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	Male	50	78.16	16.47		

calculation the t-value was 0.00215 where calculated table value was 1.96 which was greater than the t-value. So the calculation proves that there was no significant difference between levels of academic procrastination among the urban and rural male students of higher education, after calculation researcher found that the calculated mean value of urban area students are higher than the rural areas.

Bar Graph -2

* Table value 1.96 with df 98 on 0.05 level of significance.

Locale	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Significance level
Urban	Female	50	75.08	15.36	0.218	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	Female	50	78.94	15.83		

Mean of the urban female student was 75.08 where sd was 15.36 and rural female students mean was 78.94 and sd was 15.83. The t-value was 0.218 where calculated table value was 1.96 which was greater than the t-value. After calculation it proves that there was no significant difference between levels of academic procrastination among the urban and rural female students of higher education.

Bar Graph -2.1

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

In this study the researcher found that irrespective of gender and geographical area the higher secondary school students have below average score on academic procrastination. The study shows that all higher secondary school student needs counseling to overcome from academic procrastination.

CONCLUSION:

Academic procrastination is a widespread issue among higher secondary school students, significantly affecting their academic performance and emotional well-being. The study identified several key dimensions contributing to procrastination, including time management difficulties, emotional

regulation, and motivational factors. The findings underscore the importance of developing effective time management skills, fostering intrinsic motivation, and addressing psychological factors such as anxiety and perfectionism. To mitigate procrastination, educators and parents should work together to provide students with the tools and support they need to manage their academic responsibilities. Interventions such as time management training, stress reduction techniques, and motivational strategies should be integrated into school programs to help students overcome procrastination and improve their academic outcomes.

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